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Effects of Loading and Nafion Content on the Activity and Stability of Iridium Oxygen Evolution Reaction Catalysts

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Iridium (Ir) is the benchmark catalyst for the oxygen evolution reaction (OER) in proton-exchange-membrane water electrolyzers, yet its scarcity demands rigorous, reproducible benchmarking in aqueous model systems. We systematically vary catalyst loading and Nafion ionomer content to probe how ink formulation governs the activity–stability trade-off for two Ir phases: metallic Ir and IrO₂. OER activity and Ir dissolution are monitored simultaneously using online inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry, and the catalyst–ionomer interface is characterized by electron microscopy and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy. Our results show that catalyst loading has no effect on Ir dissolution, while ionomer content is the dominant and phase-dependent parameter: on metallic Ir, increasing Nafion lowers activity with no effect on dissolution, while for IrO₂, it increases both activity and dissolution. These opposing trends are consistent with ionomer-induced changes in interfacial structure, oxidation state, particle dispersion, and accessible active area. Our study shows that ionomer content and catalyst phase must be carefully controlled and reported when benchmarking Ir-based OER catalysts, and provides practical guidelines to balance performance while minimizing precious-metal loss.

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Decarbonizing hard-to-abate sectors such as heavy transportation, steel, and ammonia synthesis hinges on the large-scale availability of green hydrogen,¹ and water electrolysis is the most direct route to that goal.² Among the competing electrolyzer technologies, proton-exchange-membrane water electrolysis (PEMWE) is the most advanced, delivering high current densities in a compact, differential-pressure stack.³ Yet the technology still relies on iridium, the sole oxygen evolution reaction (OER) catalyst that combines high activity with stability under strongly acidic, oxidative environments.^{4,5} Iridium's price volatility⁶ and geological scarcity therefore dominate the cost of PEMWE stacks⁷ and threaten raw-material supply as demand scales.^{8,9}

Strategies to lower Ir loading confront a well-known activity–stability trade-off: metallic and amorphous Ir phases are highly active but dissolve readily, whereas rutile IrO₂ is significantly more stable but kinetically sluggish.^{10–12} Balancing this trade-off by developing new catalysts to meet cost targets set by agencies such as the U.S. Department of Energy¹³ requires fast, reliable screening methods. Aqueous model systems (AMS)¹⁴ and accelerated stress tests (AST)^{15,16} have become indispensable for this purpose, yet most AMS studies still prioritize activity and assess stability with simple galvanostatic holds, overlooking dissolution pathways that ultimately dictate catalyst lifetimes.¹⁷

A further complication is that the standard rotating-disk-electrode (RDE) setup in AMS exposes the catalyst to a liquid electrolyte, whereas a PEMWE anode operates at a solid Nafion-ionomer interface.¹⁸ Consequently, RDE-derived activities often translate reasonably well,¹⁹ but dissolution rates can be under- or over-estimated by orders of magnitude.^{12,20} The underlying causes: local pH mismatch,²¹ buildup of dissolved ions,⁵ microbubbles accumulation,²² and, more recently, the presence of inert mobile anions adsorbed in the double layer²³ remain debated. Bridging this

gap requires either (i) adapting AMS protocols to mimic solid-ionomer environments or (ii) explicitly de-convoluting the fundamental processes that differ between the two systems.

The ionomer itself is a frequently neglected variable. Nafion, with its fluorocarbon backbone and sulfonic-acid side chains,^{24,25} governs proton transport, water routing, and gas removal in PEMWE catalyst layers,^{26–28} yet in RDE studies it is often omitted or used merely as a dispersant and binder on inert substrates.^{5,21} Fuel-cell literature has shown that ionomer–metal interactions modulate catalytic kinetics, mass transport, and durability,^{29–33} but analogous insights under harsh OER conditions and across different Ir phases are scarce. When confined to nanometer-thick films, Nafion can change conductivity, morphology, swelling, and water uptake, thereby reshaping local reaction environments and stability windows.^{34,35} Optimal ionomer content is therefore a fine balance: too little increases ohmic losses due to hindered proton transport; too much blocks O₂ transport and raises electronic resistance.³⁶ Recent studies further showed that the Nafion-to-Ir ratio is largely dictated by the fabrication method,³⁷ and that Nafion binding strength is phase-dependent.²⁷ Specifically, Nafion swells more and improves ionic conductivity on metallic Ir, while it binds more strongly and lowers kinetic overpotentials on amorphous Ir, impacting efficiency.

Because AMS lacks the solid-ionomer triple-phase boundary of PEMWE, ionomer behavior in liquid-phase testing can deviate markedly.^{34,38} Few systematic AMS investigations exist, but the available data already show that (i) eliminating Nafion yields poorly dispersed inks that agglomerate, (ii) excessive ionomer coverage poisons active sites,¹⁹ and (iii) moderate Nafion additions improve stability in some cases²¹ yet offer little benefit in others.⁵ Clearly, a mechanistic understanding of how Nafion interactions with different Ir phases²⁷ affect dissolution is still lacking.

Here, we present a comprehensive analysis of the Ir loading and Nafion content effects on the activity and stability of commercial metallic and oxide Ir catalysts. Time-resolved dissolution is quantified with a scanning flow cell coupled to inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (SFC-ICP-MS), while benchmark RDE

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measurements provide a direct comparison to conventional AMS protocols. Scanning electron microscopy/energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (SEM-EDX), X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), and contact-angle analyses reveal changes in morphology, surface chemistry, and wettability prior to electrochemical testing.

Our objectives are threefold. First, we assess how ionomer–phase interactions across metallic Ir and Ir oxide relate to activity and dissolution. Second, we quantify the extent to which ionomer content and catalyst loading in AMS contribute to stability differences and translation errors relative to PEMWE. Third, we propose AMS-based ink formulation guidelines to minimize Ir dissolution without compromising OER kinetics, while acknowledging the limits of MEA transferability. By clarifying how the ionomer–catalyst interface governs both performance and degradation, this work advances the knowledge required to extend catalyst lifetimes and to cut Ir demand, key milestones toward cost-competitive, gigawatt-scale PEM water electrolysis.

Experimental

Electrochemical characterization.—Ink Preparation.—Catalyst inks for SFC-ICP-MS measurements were prepared by dispersing iridium black and IrO₂ powders (both from Alfa Aesar) in a 7:1 (v/v) mixture of ultrapure water (18 M Ω cm, TOC <3 ppb; Merck, Milli-Q IQ 7000) and isopropanol ($\geq 99.8\%$, Emsure[®], Merck). Prior to dispersion, IrO₂ powder was thermally treated in tube furnace at 600 °C for 12 h, based on previous protocol,¹² but with a reduced duration (from 48 h) to maintain dissolution levels within the detection limits of ICP-MS. To investigate the effect of catalyst loading, a 5 wt% perfluorinated Nafion ionomer solution (Ion Power GmbH) was added at a catalyst-to-ionomer weight ratio of 10:1 (corresponding to 10 wt% Nafion). Inks were formulated to reach final iridium concentrations of 663, 2655, and 9291 mg l⁻¹, corresponding to target loadings of 10, 40, and 140 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$, respectively. To study the influence of Nafion content, the metal concentration was fixed at 2655 mg l⁻¹ (equivalent to 40 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$), while Nafion content was varied by adjusting the catalyst-to-ionomer weight ratio to 10:1, 2.5:1, and 0.714:1, corresponding to 10, 40, and 140 wt% Nafion, respectively. All inks were dispersed using probe sonication (Branson SFX150) in an ice bath for 15 min with a pulsed sequence (4 s on/2 s off), followed by pH adjustment to ~ 11 using 1 M KOH.³⁹ For electrode preparation, 0.2 μl aliquots of each ink were drop-cast onto mirror-polished gold foil substrates (25 \times 25 mm, 99.95%, Alfa Aesar). Spot diameters (~ 1.3 mm) and surface morphology were characterized using a Keyence VK-X250 laser profilometer.

The ink formulation for RDE measurements followed the same general procedure as for the SFC samples, with a modified solvent composition. Specifically, the water-to-isopropanol ratio was adjusted to 3:1. This increased IPA content improved ink wettability and facilitated more uniform spreading across the larger electrode surface. Inks with various metal concentrations tailored for different loadings, for example, 196.3 mg l⁻¹ for a target loading of 10 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$, were then sonicated in an ultrasonic bath for 20 min while cooled in an ice-water bath. Following sonication, the pH was adjusted to ~ 11 using 1 M KOH.³⁹ A volume of 10 μl of each ink was drop-cast onto a cleaned gold RDE tip (Pine Research) to match the catalyst loadings and Nafion contents used in the SFC samples. During drop-casting and ambient drying, the electrode was kept stationary (i.e., not rotated), as this approach resulted in more uniform films under our conditions, despite previous reports suggesting that rotation may improve film quality.⁴⁰ To ensure consistent film quality, the dried spots were inspected with an optical microscope, and only morphologically uniform films were selected for electrochemical measurements.

SFC-ICP-MS.—Iridium stability was assessed using a custom-designed Scanning Flow Cell (SFC) coupled online to an Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometer (ICP-MS; NexION 350X and

300X, PerkinElmer), enabling time-resolved detection of dissolved metal species. Detailed schematics and performance validation of the SFC-ICP-MS setup have been reported in prior studies.^{41,42} Electrochemical protocols were carried out using a Biologic VSP-150 potentiostat in an Ar-saturated 0.05 M H₂SO₄ electrolyte, freshly prepared by diluting concentrated Suprapur-grade acid (96%, Merck) with ultrapure water (18.2 M Ω , TOC <3 ppb). Substrates with drop-cast catalyst spots (as described in the preceding section) were positioned using a high-precision XYZ translation stage to align with the 0.033 cm² SFC opening. A graphite rod (HTW Sigradur G) functioned as the counter electrode, while a Metrohm double-junction Ag/AgCl electrode (inner: 3 M KCl; outer: 0.05 M H₂SO₄) served as the reference. All potentials were converted to the RHE scale by daily referencing against a hydrogen-saturated Pt foil in the same electrolyte. Electrolyte was delivered at a constant rate of $\sim 3.5 \mu\text{l s}^{-1}$ via the ICP-MS peristaltic pump and mixed in-line with an internal standard (1:1 volume ratio). Calibration was performed daily using freshly prepared standards at 0.5, 1, and 5 ppb (Certipur, Merck). Internal standardization with ¹⁸⁷Re (10 $\mu\text{g l}^{-1}$) compensated for instrumental drift and plasma matrix effects, selected due to its physicochemical similarity to the analyte. Measured current densities were referenced to the geometric surface area of the electrode, and all measurements were repeated at least three times to ensure reproducibility. No iR compensation was applied, as the absolute currents and ohmic resistances were low, resulting in a negligible potential drop.

RDE.—RDE experiments were performed in a custom three-electrode PTFE cell connected to a modulated speed rotator (Pine Research). Au disk electrodes ($\varnothing \approx 5$ mm, Pine Research) embedded in PTFE holders served as the working electrodes and were mirror-polished with alumina before each measurement to ensure reproducibility. The reference and counter electrodes (see previous section) were separated from the working compartment by a Luggin capillary and a membrane to prevent contamination by Cl⁻ ions and Ir redeposition. The electrolyte, 0.05 M H₂SO₄ (diluted from 96% Suprapure, Merck), was purged with argon for at least 30 min prior to testing and kept under continuous argon flow throughout the measurements. Ohmic resistance was determined via electrochemical impedance spectroscopy, and 85% of the iR drop was compensated in situ. Electrode rotation was maintained at 1600 rpm, and measurements were controlled using a Biologic SP-300 potentiostat. For post-mortem analysis, 2 ml electrolyte aliquots were collected for offline ICP-MS. Between experiments, the electrodes were repolished and re-coated with fresh catalyst ink, and all cell components were cleaned by boiling in 1% HNO₃, followed by multiple ultrapure water rinses.

Surface characterization.—XPS.—X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) measurements were carried out using an EnviroESCA system (SPECS), equipped with a Phoibos 160 NAP 1D-DLD hemispherical electron analyzer and a monochromatic Al K α X-ray source with an energy of 1486.7 eV. The measurements were performed under ultra-high vacuum (UHV) conditions at a pressure of approximately 10⁻⁷ Pa. The acquired core-level spectra were analyzed using the KolXP software. For energy calibration, the Ir 4f spectra were referenced to Au 5p from the substrate, while the F 1s, O 1s, and C 1s regions were aligned to the F 1s peak to account for differential charging of Nafion.

SEM-EDX.—The morphology was examined using a Mira 3 (Tescan) scanning electron microscope (SEM) operating at the primary electron energy set at 30 keV. Elemental composition and distribution were analyzed by energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) with an XFlash 610 detector (Bruker) integrated into the SEM.

Contact angle.—A drop shape analyzer (DSA30) from Krüss was used for contact angle measurements with their ADVANCE

software. The measurements were performed using the sessile drop method, tangent fitting, and an automatic baseline fitting for the contact angles. Water droplets were used to quantify the contact angles, and a gold foil with the different iridium spots was used as the substrate.

X-ray diffraction (XRD).—Measurements were performed on a Panalytical Empyrean 2 in Bragg–Brentano geometry using Cu K α radiation at 2θ angles between 20 and 80°.

Results and Discussion

Influence of catalyst loading.—Although Ir metal and Ir oxide OER catalysts have been studied extensively, the combined influence of catalyst loading and ionomer content on activity and stability remain unresolved. Here, we address this gap starting with a systematic variation of the metallic Ir loading on an exponential scale, spanning both commonly used lower values and higher extremes. Increasing the loading from 10 to 140 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ thickens the film and proportionally raises the integrated anodic charge (Q_a) measured in cyclic voltammograms (CV) (Fig. 1a, left).

Throughout this work, the Q_a is used as a quantitative proxy for electrochemical surface area (ECSA). Although Q_a inevitably includes double-layer and pseudocapacitive contributions,⁴³ its linear scaling with catalyst loading under otherwise identical preparation conditions makes it a practical metric for relative comparisons. Accordingly, every reference to “ECSA-normalized” data should be read as “ Q_a -normalized” (i.e., charge-normalized).

When the voltammograms are normalized by ECSA, the profiles overlap, confirming that the additional charge in thicker CLs originates mainly from a larger number of chemically identical surface sites. The geometric OER current therefore scales with loading (Fig. 1a, right).⁴⁴ This increase, however, does not translate into higher mass- or ECSA-normalized activity. At low overpotentials, the normalized curves overlap (Fig. S1), but at higher overpotentials, the thicker films show increasingly lower mass-specific

activity because ECSA per mass decreases with film thickness (Fig. S2a), likely due to mass transport limitations and/or inefficient exposure of active sites.¹⁹ The simultaneous drop in site-specific activity (Fig. 1a,) suggests additional transport limitations, most plausibly micro-bubble coverage and O₂ accumulation that transiently block active sites.⁴⁵ Therefore, intrinsic OER kinetics should be benchmarked at current densities low enough to avoid such artefacts, yet within a potential window where the current originates predominantly from water oxidation rather than Ir oxidation or other parasitic reactions. A more robust approach is to perform galvanostatic steps long enough for capacitive and Ir oxidation currents to decay to negligible levels, ensuring that the measured current reflects the true steady-state OER. The required hold time may increase with catalyst loading, and careful consideration of higher overpotentials or currents could be necessary, but steady-state conditions must be confirmed. Accordingly, benchmarking should favor low scan rates or, preferably, stepped protocols that ensure quasi-steady-state conditions, in line with the polarization-curve recommended for applied systems by Malkow et al.⁴⁶

Stability tests at 5 mA cm⁻² for three minutes offer additional insights. During the hold, the overpotential decreases logarithmically with increasing Ir loading (Figs. S3c, S3d), displaying classic Tafel behavior even at these high OER rates. The extracted slope of 58 mV dec⁻¹ closely matches the Tafel slope obtained from LSV measurements (Fig. S1), in line with previous reports.⁴⁷ This confirms that the overpotential shift with loading is primarily kinetic. Because Q_a scales linearly with Ir loading, increasing the loading from 10 to 140 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ proportionally increases the number of accessible active sites, thereby reducing the local current density and the overpotential.³⁶ The surface-area-normalized Ir dissolution triggered by OER remains essentially independent of loading (Fig. 1b, right). As thicker layers distribute the same current across more sites, the local turnover frequency, and therefore the dissolution driving force, decreases (Fig. S2b). Accordingly, mass-normalized dissolution scales linearly with both mass- and ECSA-normalized

Figure 1. Catalyst loading of metallic Ir influences OER activity and dissolution. (a) CVs (0.4–1.4 V_{RHE}, 50 mV s⁻¹) and LSVs (1.2–1.55 V_{RHE}, 10 mV s⁻¹) normalized by geometric area, Ir mass, and anodic charge. (b) Representative electrochemical protocol (the potential during the hold shifts with loading, see Fig. S3), real-time Ir dissolution measured by SFC-ICP-MS, and Ir dissolution amount during 5 mA cm⁻² hold. (c) Percentage loss of OER current at 1.55 V_{RHE} and corresponding ECSA loss after the hold, estimated from LSVs and CVs, respectively. All measurements were performed using the SFC-ICP-MS setup.

current densities (Fig. S3b) but not with the geometric current density (Fig. S3a).

Interestingly, during CV, transient Ir dissolution increases with catalyst loading (Fig. 1b, arrow), in contrast to the galvanostatic hold. The two processes therefore scale differently: transient dissolution⁴⁸ scales with the ECSA, whereas OER-induced dissolution is governed by the absolute current distributed over the ECSA and remains independent of potential within this range. The S-number, defined as evolved O₂ per dissolved Ir atom (triggered by OER but not transient dissolution),¹² remains constant across all loadings (Fig. 1b), consistent in both trend and values with prior work using the same mass-normalized currents.²¹ The absence of the loading-dependent stability gain reported by El-Sayed et al. indicates that microbubble shielding, if present, is insufficient to suppress OER-triggered dissolution under these conditions.⁴⁹ Our results also contrast with applied systems (PEMWE), where lower Ir loadings have been linked to higher dissolution. We attribute this to solid-ionomer interfaces and the much lower effective Ir-ion diffusivity in ionomer relative to water: thicker, ionomer-containing catalyst layers at higher loadings impede outward transport, promote local re-deposition, and shift the dissolution/re-deposition equilibrium,^{50,51} an effect largely absent in AMS, where high Ir-ion diffusivity ensures rapid outward transport regardless of catalyst layer thickness. Accordingly, future AMS studies should incorporate ionomer overlayers of defined thickness or ionomer-mimicking barriers on Ir films to better reproduce the mass-transport limitations and interfacial characteristics of MEAs.

The OER activity loss, however, depends on loading. After the galvanostatic hold, the geometric activity of the 10 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ sample decreases by nearly 30%, whereas the 40 and 140 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ loadings lose $\sim 10\%$ (Fig. 1c, left). Normalizing the currents to ECSA aligns the three activity losses, confirming that the loss arises from a reduction in accessible surface area. Because dissolution is minimal (0.01%–0.04% to the total loading, Fig. S3b), the most plausible cause is further oxidation of Ir³⁺ to the less active Ir⁴⁺ species,⁵² recently identified as the dominant degradation pathway in nanoparticulate Ir catalysts.⁵³ Such oxidation most likely leads to the formation of more compact Ir oxide, less susceptible to ion incorporation during the pseudocapacitive charge/discharge processes. At low loading, higher local potentials likely accelerate oxidation, while the accompanying change in surface hydrophilicity may hinder bubble detachment and intensify ECSA loss.⁴⁵ Agglomeration could also reduce ECSA without affecting dissolution,⁵⁴ but this mechanism should intensify, not diminish, at higher loadings, where interparticle distances are shorter.⁵⁵ High-resolution microscopy before and after testing is required to distinguish and understand the oxidation-induced site loss in Ir oxide.

Although SFC experiments form the core of this study, repeating the protocol in an RDE confirms the generality of the main trends. CV, LSV, and galvanostatic data reproduce the SFC results for activity and stability (Figs. S4, S5). Given the larger RDE spot area (0.196 cm² vs ~ 0.033 cm² in SFC), we adjusted the IPA/H₂O ratio in RDE to control viscosity and wetting. Although such changes can influence aggregation and ionomer adsorption, the consistent trends across setups indicate that any resulting effects are minor. However, three discrepancies emerge: (i) The intrinsic activity of the 10 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ film improves after the stability test, rather than declining as observed in the SFC. The higher overpotential during the 5 mA cm⁻² hold (Figs. S3c, S5b) indicates lower film quality in the RDE, where fewer Ir sites are electrochemically connected. During OER, vigorous O₂ evolution under rotation may restructure the loosely packed layer: bubbles nucleate and collapse within the film, mechanically improving particle connectivity and activating previously isolated Ir³⁺ sites. This restructuring likely accounts for the observed increase in intrinsic activity, in contrast to the decline seen in the higher-quality SFC film. (ii) Total Ir dissolution measured offline increases linearly with loading under RDE conditions (it is explained by considering additional transient dissolution during the

potential sweeps, which cannot be separated in offline studies (Fig. 1b)). (iii) The mass- and ECSA-normalized polarization curves do not overlap at low overpotentials as observed in SFC (Fig. 1a). Tafel analysis clarifies this deviation: while the overpotential at 5 mA cm⁻² again decreases logarithmically with loading (Fig. S5c), as in the SFC, the slightly higher slope observed in the RDE suggests lower catalyst utilization or layer inhomogeneity, as also indicated by the lower mass-normalized charge (Figs. S2a and S5a), and/or additional ohmic or transport resistances.

Because such transport penalties often originate from differences in catalyst-layer structure, we next examined how the ink drop-casting protocol influences RDE film morphology and performance. Figure S6 shows an alternative approach to achieving higher RDE loadings, successive drop-casts of a dilute ink, compared to the single deposition of a concentrated ink used in Fig. S4. With the multi-step protocol, both ECSA and OER activity decline with increasing loading, whereas the single-step method yields the expected increase. We attribute this discrepancy to differences in local Nafion content and distribution, which are examined in the second part of this study. All SFC and RDE experiments were repeated on glassy carbon, reproducing the same trends, indicating that substrate passivation is minimal here and far less pronounced than during ASTs.¹⁵

In summary, increasing the Ir loading improves geometric current density but has little effect on mass-specific or intrinsic activity at low overpotentials. At higher overpotentials, however, both decline due to transport limitations and incomplete utilization. Consequently, meaningful comparisons of mass- or ECSA-normalized activity across the literature should be performed at moderate overpotentials, low enough to minimize transport artefacts, but still high enough for the current to originate predominantly from water oxidation rather than Ir oxidation or other parasitic processes. Ideally, such benchmarking should be performed using stepped polarization curves with hold times long enough to reach steady-state OER, free from contributions of these processes, including capacitive currents. Achieving this may require extended durations and, in some cases, careful consideration of higher overpotentials or currents, depending on the catalyst loading.

Higher loadings also offer no intrinsic stability advantage, even though they may extend device lifetime by lowering the dissolution rate per unit mass. Rather than the absolute Ir content, OER-induced dissolution is governed by the local current density, that is, the current per electrochemically active Ir site. Thus, extending device lifetime is better achieved by maximizing catalyst utilization, i.e., increasing the fraction of Ir that turns over, rather than by simply depositing thicker layers. In contrast, transient dissolution observed during potential sweeps scales with the number of electrochemically accessible Ir surface atoms.

These findings suggest that the low Ir loadings typical of AMS can be employed without the dissolution penalties reported for low-loading MEAs, although the mechanistic basis for this difference requires further investigation. One likely factor is the Ir–Nafion interfacial structure: changes in Nafion content and distribution, which often accompany variations in loading, can alter film porosity, electronic connectivity of Ir particles, and wetting. Motivated by a recent report on Nafion binding to metallic, oxidic, and amorphous Ir phases,²⁷ we therefore proceed to isolate the effect of ionomer by systematically varying Nafion content at fixed Ir loading, and by repeating measurements on thermally formed IrO₂ layers.

Influence of nafion content.—With the Ir loading fixed at 40 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$, we first examined how Nafion content (0–140 wt%), chosen similarly to the loading range, affects oxygen-evolution activity and the electrochemical stability of metallic Ir (Fig. 2).

Even the initial addition of ionomer reduces the ECSA (Figs. 2a and S7a), consistent with earlier reports.⁵⁶ This decline is attributed to Nafion's low electronic conductivity²⁵ and the insulating layer it forms: the polymer disrupts particle-to-particle and particle-to-substrate contacts,^{29,57,58} blocks active Ir sites,^{59,60} and, once a

Figure 2. Nafion content controls OER performance and dissolution of metallic Ir. (a) CVs (0.4–1.4 V_{RHE} , 50 $mV s^{-1}$) and LSVs (1.2–1.55 V_{RHE} , 10 $mV s^{-1}$) normalized by geometric area, Ir mass, and anodic charge. (b) Representative electrochemical protocol (the potential during the hold shifts with Nafion content, see Fig. S7), real-time Ir dissolution measured by SFC-ICP-MS, and Ir dissolution during 5 $mA cm^{-2}$ hold. (c) Percentage loss of OER current at 1.55 V_{RHE} and corresponding ECSA loss after the hold, estimated from LSVs and CVs, respectively. All measurements were performed using the SFC-ICP-MS.

certain percolation threshold is exceeded, constricts pores and promotes nanoparticle agglomeration,^{29,59,61} all of which reduce the accessible surface area.⁵⁶ Geometric- and mass-normalized OER activities decline in parallel with ECSA (Fig. S7a),⁵⁶ and even the ECSA-normalized activity follows this trend, except at 140 wt% Nafion, where an unexpected increase is observed (Fig. 2a, right). One possible explanation is that the local pH at high Nafion contents becomes more alkaline (by ~ 0.5 pH units). While Nafion is a strong-acid polymer, effective proton activity in its hydrated domains may be lower due to water-dependent transport along sulfonic-lined channels and ion pairing. As a result, assuming pH 1 for RHE conversion could underestimate the true overpotential, consistent with the lower OER onset in Fig. 2a (bottom). Alternatively, excess Nafion may inhibit sulfate adsorption,⁶² thereby lowering the OER onset potential.

Turning to stability, Ir OER dissolution during the 5 $mA cm^{-2}$ hold decreases as the Nafion content increases from 0 to 40 wt% (Fig. 2b), but rises nearly threefold at 140 wt%. Because the S-number remains constant up to 40 wt%, the dominant OER dissolution pathway⁶³ appears unaffected. The decrease instead reflects a declining number of accessible sites (Fig. S7a). This interpretation is supported by the slight increase in intrinsic current and potential during the hold (Figs. S7b, S7c), which correlates well with the lower site utilization at higher Nafion contents, as described by a Tafel-type relationship proposed by Bernt et al. (Eq. 10 in ref. 36), where overpotential varies logarithmically with accessible charge.³⁶ A similar trend is evident from the linear correlation observed for all ≤ 40 wt% data when ECSA-normalized current is plotted against surface area-normalized dissolution (Fig. S8). Beyond 40 wt%, however, the simple “fewer-sites” picture breaks down. At 140 wt% Nafion, the accessible surface drops sharply, so sustaining the 5 $mA cm^{-2}$ hold requires a 13-fold higher intrinsic current (Fig. S7c), driving the potential to 1.80 V_{RHE} (Fig. S7b). Simultaneously, the S-number drops by nearly half an order of magnitude (Fig. 2b, right). In other words, OER dissolution that is essentially potential-independent below $\sim 1.65 V_{RHE}$ becomes

strongly potential-dependent once the electrode is driven to $\geq 1.80 V_{RHE}$, indicating the activation of an additional high-potential dissolution pathway, most plausibly the formation and loss of soluble Ir^{6+} species.⁶³

The high potential reached during the galvanostatic hold also influences transient dissolution. Before the hold, the 140 wt% Nafion sample shows negligible Ir dissolution during CVs from 0.40 to 1.40 V_{RHE} , the lowest among all samples (Fig. 2d). As previously discussed, transient dissolution scales with the ECSA, which is lowest in this sample (Fig. S7a), explaining the initially low signal. However, as a result of the high potential reached during the hold ($\geq 1.80 V_{RHE}$), the surface likely undergoes greater oxidation, either forming a larger fraction of Ir^{4+} , oxidizing to higher-valent states such as Ir^{5+} , or both. Upon sweeping the potential back to 0.40 V_{RHE} , the reduction of these highly oxidized species triggers significant cathodic dissolution, resulting in a pronounced transient dissolution that exceeds those observed for samples with lower Nafion content.

Beyond dissolution, the stability test also affects activity and ECSA (Fig. 2c). The 10 wt% and 40 wt% Nafion samples retain their initial ECSA (as shown above for identical loading and ionomer content), whereas the Nafion-free film shows a net increase. In the absence of ionomer to bind the particles, mechanical effects from O_2 bubble evolution can move loosely anchored agglomerates and create micro-cracks in the catalyst film, or restructure the entire layer into a more porous configuration.^{61,64,65} These changes expose previously inaccessible particles to the electrolyte, increasing the measured ECSA. Apparent ECSA also increases at 140 wt%, where ionomer-catalyst segregation⁶⁶ triggers interfacial reconstruction⁵⁶ and partial ionomer leaching,⁶⁶ uncovering additional sites. Normalizing the post-hold current by ECSA shows an intrinsic activity loss in every sample: the decay is smallest at 10 wt%, larger at 40 wt%, and greatest at the two extremes. We ascribe the larger drops to agglomeration (0 wt%) or site blocking (140 wt%), both of which increase local potentials and accelerate passivation to less

active Ir^{4+} species. Considering stable ECSA, dissolution, minimal intrinsic-activity loss, and OER activities matching the binder-free Ref., 10 wt% Nafion is the optimum for metallic Ir. Mass-normalized activities, however, decrease as ionomer loading rises, so comparisons to other studies should cite geometric or intrinsic metrics alongside mass-based values. RDE measurements (Figs. S9, S10) confirm the SFC trends in potential, dissolution, activity, and mass-normalized ECSA. The only deviation appears at ECSA loss after the stability test.

To isolate the effect of ionomer distribution, we compared RDE films prepared by premixing 10 wt% Nafion into the catalyst ink with those top-coated after deposition. Notably, the ECSA is identical in both cases (Fig. S11), suggesting that the brief wetting–drying cycle during top-coating either redistributes the catalyst or partially dissolves and redeposits Ir, resulting in ionomer coverage comparable to that of the premixed film. This finding contrasts with a previous report claiming higher utilization from post-deposition ionomer, attributed to preserved electronic connectivity between catalyst particles and the conductive substrate.⁶⁷

To determine whether the ionomer-induced trends observed for metallic Ir hold for pre-oxidized catalysts, the full protocol was repeated using thermally prepared IrO_2 (Fig. 3). The results show that Nafion's interaction with IrO_2 differs significantly.

Between 0 and 40 wt% Nafion, the geometric CVs are largely unchanged, with a clear decline only at 140 wt% (Fig. 3a). By contrast, mass-normalized CVs show a consistent decrease in ECSA (Fig. S12a) with increasing Nafion content. Yet over the same range, both geometric- and mass-normalized OER currents increase, indicating that activity improves even as accessible surface area declines. At 140 wt%, this trend reverses, and activity drops in parallel with the ECSA loss. Normalization by ECSA confirms that Nafion improves the intrinsic activity of IrO_2 , unlike metallic Ir, where a comparable increase appears only at 140 wt%, suggesting a surface modification specific to the oxide.

The stability trends of IrO_2 differ notably from those of metallic Ir. Within 0–40 wt% Nafion, Ir OER dissolution increases steadily,

including during the initial contact peaks, and remains independent of applied potential as well as geometric, mass-, and ECSA-normalized currents (Figs. 3b, S12b, and S12c). This trend is accompanied by a decrease in S-numbers (discussed later), confirming a loss of intrinsic stability. The increase in contact peak dissolution to values comparable to, or even exceeding, those of metallic Ir further suggests a degradation mechanism linked to Nafion interaction. At 140 wt%, OER activity becomes insufficient to sustain the applied current, forcing the reaction onto the Au substrate and driving the potential beyond $2.0 V_{\text{RHE}}$. These data are therefore excluded from the analysis.

After the galvanostatic hold, ECSA increases in every sample, although the gain diminishes as Nafion content increases. This trend may reflect weaker binding at lower Nafion contents, where O_2 bubbles can restructure and rearrange agglomerates. As particles are displaced, the likelihood of forming new electronic contacts increases, thereby exposing or reconnecting previously inactive Ir sites. Geometric- and intrinsic-activity losses follow the same trend. Overall, Nafion preserves stability but suppresses activity in metallic Ir, whereas in IrO_2 it improves activity at the expense of accelerated dissolution. Despite the intrinsic-activity gain, excessive ionomer ultimately impairs both catalysts by blocking active sites and promoting dissolution. For both materials, 10 wt% Nafion offers the most favorable trade-off between activity and stability. This is consistent with previous PEMWE studies, which also identified an optimal ionomer content around 11.6 wt%.³⁶

To better understand these opposing trends, we correlated electrochemical data with surface characterization (Fig. 4).

SEM shows that IrO_2 films drop-cast without Nafion form large aggregates, while adding ionomer progressively de-agglomerates the particles (Figs. 4a, S13) and improves dispersion.^{27,36} At 140 wt%, however, Nafion forms a continuous layer that envelops most agglomerates. A similar coating forms on metallic Ir, as evident from low-magnification images (Fig. S14), though its morphology remains largely unchanged across the same range (Fig. 4b). In both Ir and IrO_2 films, higher Nafion content leads to a more pronounced

Figure 3. Nafion content controls OER performance and dissolution of IrO_2 . (a) CVs ($0.4\text{--}1.4 V_{\text{RHE}}$, 50 mV s^{-1}) and LSVs ($1.2\text{--}1.55 V_{\text{RHE}}$, 10 mV s^{-1}) normalized by geometric area, Ir mass and anodic charge. (b) Representative electrochemical protocol (the potential during the hold shifts with Nafion content, see Fig. S12), real-time Ir dissolution measured by SFC-ICP-MS, and Ir dissolution during 5 mA cm^{-2} hold. (c) Percentage loss of OER current at $1.55 V_{\text{RHE}}$ and corresponding ECSA loss after the hold, estimated from LSVs and CVs, respectively. All measurements were performed using the SFC-ICP-MS.

Figure 4. Influence of nafion content on the surface properties of metallic Ir and IrO₂. SEM images of (a) IrO₂ and (b) Metallic Ir at varying Nafion contents. (c) Corresponding EDX (left), XPS (middle), and contact angle (right) analyses as functions of Nafion content. All measurements were performed on drop-cast spots used in SFC-ICP-MS experiments.

coffee-ring effect (Figs. S15 and S16). This is generally attributed to capillary flow and uneven solvent evaporation at the droplet edge during drying. The addition of Nafion ionomer likely exacerbates this effect by increasing the ink's viscosity and modifying its surface tension. We acknowledge, however, that other physical factors such as substrate wetting and drying kinetics also play a role.

SEM-EDX elemental mapping confirms that these morphological differences correlate closely with variations in Nafion distribution, showing clear enrichment on IrO₂ agglomerates (Figs. S17, S18). Quantitative EDX over a 50 × 50 μm area shows that the atomic F/Ir ratio is much higher for IrO₂ (~2.7) than for metallic Ir (~0.25) at 40 wt% Nafion (Fig. 4c, left). Surface-sensitive XPS shows the same trend at the outermost ~5 nm (Figs. S19, S20), with calculated F/Ir and CF_x/Ir ratios also increasing with Nafion loading,⁶⁴ and both approximately twice as high on IrO₂ (Figs. 4c and S21). These complementary results indicate greater Nafion accumulation on the IrO₂ surface. Consistently, at 40 wt% Nafion, the Ir 4f intensity decreases for IrO₂, implying thicker Nafion surface coverage, whereas it increases slightly for metallic Ir (Fig. S19).

Motivated by the morphology and ionomer-distribution trends, we analyzed the surface chemistry by XPS of the Ir 4f region using the fitting procedure in Ref. 68 (Figs. S19 and S20). IrO₂ without Nafion shows only an Ir⁴⁺ doublet. At 10 wt% Nafion, a second doublet due to Ir³⁺ appears, and the spectrum is dominated by Ir⁴⁺ with a smaller Ir³⁺ contribution (~80% Ir⁴⁺ and ~20% Ir³⁺), consistent with amorphous iridium oxide (Fig. S22).⁶⁸ Metallic Ir shows a broader envelope with contributions from Ir⁴⁺, Ir³⁺, and Ir⁰. The most intense component corresponds to Ir⁴⁺, indicating surface oxidation after drop-casting and aligning with reports of a decreasing Ir⁰ fraction and increasing Ir⁴⁺.⁶⁹ With increasing Nafion content, the Ir³⁺ fraction on IrO₂ grows, whereas the surface composition of metallic Ir remains unchanged (Fig. S22).

Powder X-ray diffraction (XRD) was used to determine the bulk structure of the powders prior to ink preparation (Fig. S23). Ir black shows reflections of metallic fcc Ir. The peak shape combines sharp and broad components, consistent with a bimodal size distribution of larger crystallites and smaller nanoparticles.⁶⁹ The as-received IrO₂ powder displays the same sharp metallic Ir reflections together with very faint, broadened intensity at the expected positions of rutile-type IrO₂, indicating that the oxidic fraction is largely X-ray

amorphous. Upon calcination, well-defined rutile-IrO₂ reflections emerge while the metallic peaks remain unchanged, consistent with crystallization of the amorphous oxide without altering the metallic core.⁶⁸ Importantly, powder XRD is insensitive to ultrathin, poorly ordered hydrated/oxyhydroxide surface layers, as detected by XPS.

Together with the activity and stability (S-) numbers, the surface-sensitive XPS and bulk XRD data indicate that the “metallic” powder is metallic in the bulk, while its surface region contains a mixture of metallic with amorphous oxyhydroxide. The “oxide” powder shows rutile IrO₂ in the bulk after calcination, whereas its surface is predominantly amorphous IrO_x after drop-casting. For the discussion below, we therefore treat the metallic powder as predominantly metallic and the oxide powder as primarily amorphous IrO_x at the surface.

Particle agglomeration in the drop-cast spot is controlled by the interplay between van der Waals attraction and electrostatic repulsion, both influenced by Nafion adsorption and ionomer conformation in the ink.⁷⁰ Because Nafion binds more strongly to hydroxylated amorphous iridium oxide, presumably through hydrogen bonding or electrostatic attraction between -SO₃H and surface -OH groups,²⁷ it adsorbs uniformly across the particles (Fig. 4c). This continuous coating increases the ink's ζ-potential, amplifies electrostatic repulsion, and suppresses van der Waals forces,⁷⁰ thereby stabilizing the dispersion,^{56,71} yielding smaller, more evenly separated agglomerates (Fig. 4a). Once the surface is saturated, however, excess ionomer segregates into micellar patches that block active sites (Figs. S7, S12),⁵⁶ as further evidenced by the diminished Ir 4f XPS signal (Fig. S19).

Although ionomer adsorption increases intrinsic activity, it simultaneously appears to compromise intrinsic stability. One plausible explanation is that amorphous iridium oxide undergoes partial chemical reduction during ink formulation, facilitated by the solvent environment and influenced by the presence of Nafion, as evidenced by XPS (Fig. S22). Similar effects have been reported in Mn-based systems, including Mn-containing complexes⁷² and a trimetallic MnFeNi catalyst,⁷³ where the oxidation state decreased from Mn⁴⁺ to Mn²⁺ during ink preparation. This change was not attributed to Nafion's acidity or to disproportionation, but rather to interactions with electron-donating species in the ink. In addition, Nafion has been proposed to accelerate transition-metal dissolution in inks by locally increasing proton activity.⁷⁴ Accordingly, potential pre-deposition interactions that promote IrO₂ instability require in-depth future study.

Figure 5. Summary of ionomer–catalyst interactions and their impact on ink properties, film morphology, and electrochemical performance of metallic and amorphous iridium.

Because Nafion adsorbs only weakly on metallic Ir agglomerates,²⁷ XPS indicates a consistently low F/Ir ratio (Fig. 4c), and SEM shows intact agglomerates irrespective of ionomer content (Fig. 4b). This insufficient interfacial coverage fails to properly stabilize or disperse the catalyst,⁵⁸ while excess ionomer segregates into polymer-rich domains. This increases ionic strength and lowers the ink ζ -potential, further compromising dispersion stability.⁷⁵ Hence, the decline in ECSA (Fig. S7) and mass activity (Fig. 2a) is due to three factors: catalyst agglomeration that blocks internal sites, non-uniform deposition from the coffee-ring effect, and direct site blocking by segregated Nafion domains. Potential mitigation strategies include tailoring the ink formulation, for example, by optimizing the solvent composition to suppress inverse-micelle formation,⁷⁶ or surface functionalization, such as NH_x-doped carbon, to strengthen Nafion binding and promote more uniform ionomer distribution.⁷⁷ Notably, unlike amorphous iridium oxide, the S-number of metallic Ir remains largely unchanged with increasing Nafion content (Fig. 2b). Although metallic Ir is already in the reduced state, its surface can become partially oxidized upon air exposure.⁷⁸ These native oxides are more readily and completely reduced back to Ir⁰ during ink preparation than amorphous IrO_x, which contains Ir in higher oxidation states (Ir³⁺ and Ir⁴⁺). As a result, the initial oxidation state of metallic Ir remains consistent across samples, explaining the similar S-numbers.

Contact-angle goniometry confirms these adsorption trends (Fig. 4c, right and Fig. S21). We acknowledge that contact angles on Nafion are sensitive to measurement time,⁷⁹ ambient humidity,⁸⁰ and surface roughness.⁸¹ All measurements were conducted in a single session under nominally constant humidity using mirror-polished Au substrate to minimize variability. Nonetheless, as we recorded only static (not advancing/receding) contact angles, the data should be interpreted cautiously. On hydroxylated IrO_x, strong –SO₃H anchoring

likely exposes the hydrophobic backbone, and the apparent angle increases nearly linearly with ionomer loading, consistent with uniform, high coverage.^{66,82} By contrast, on metallic Ir the angles remain low and even decrease at high Nafion content, in line with weak sulfonate binding, ionomer agglomeration at the surface, and phase-segregated patches that dominate the wetting response.

In summary, Nafion modulates Ir catalyst performance via two oxidation-state-dependent pathways (Fig. 5): (i) On hydroxylated IrO_x, strong chemisorption improves dispersion, increasing both activity and dissolution at moderate loadings. However, excess ionomer oversaturates the surface and impedes reactant transport. (ii) On metallic Ir, weak adsorption results in no change in agglomeration but leads to ionomer segregation into polymer-rich domains and partial site blockage, reducing ECSA and mass activity while leaving intrinsic kinetics and stability largely unaffected. For both catalysts, higher Nafion contents intensify coffee-ring formation.

Conclusions

In conclusion, we systematically examined how Ir loading and Nafion ionomer content affect OER activity and stability in metallic Ir and IrO₂ under AMS conditions. Ir loading does not influence intrinsic stability of metallic Ir. Instead, activity losses at higher loadings and overpotentials are caused by mass-transport limitations that reduce the apparent activity.

In contrast, Nafion content plays a critical role in shaping film morphology, catalyst utilization, and degradation through phase-specific interactions. For IrO₂, strong interactions with the ionomer during ink formulation improve dispersion and lead to partial chemical reduction of the oxide. This increases intrinsic activity but decreases stability. For metallic Ir, weak ionomer binding does

not prevent agglomeration and reduces activity, while stability only declines at the highest Nafion contents. At both phases, increasing Nafion content promotes coffee-ring formation, which leads to nonuniform films with lower electrochemically active surface area.

Reliable activity benchmarking requires stepped-polarization measurements at moderate overpotentials with sufficiently long hold times to reach steady-state. Ionomer content should always be reported alongside mass-normalized and, when possible, intrinsic activity metrics. In the studied range, 10 wt% Nafion provides the best compromise between activity and stability for both catalyst phases, consistent with trends observed in PEMWE systems.

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